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Effect Of Health Education On Knowledge Of Health Hazards Among Cement Factory Workers In Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

Cement factory workers face a serious and growing threat from the dust-filled air and heavy machinery in their work environment despite significant advancements in occupational safety. This study examined the effect of health education on knowledge of health hazards cement factory workers in Port Harcourt metropolis. A quasi-experimental research design, utilizing a one-group pretest-posttest approach, was employed. The study was conducted among a total population of 3600 cement workers from Dangote Cement Plc, Ibeto Cement, and BUA Cement Plc. A multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted for this study comprising simple random sampling, proportionate sampling technique and purposive sampling. A sample size of 206 participants was determined using Cochran's formula, and respondents were selected through a simple random sampling and proportionate sampling technique. Data collection was conducted using a validated self-structured test instrument titled "Questionnaire on Knowledge of Health Hazards" with a reliability index of 0.75. Data were analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) V-27 employing frequencies and percentages and Analysis of Covariance. The findings revealed a significant improvement in knowledge, highlighting substantial improvements across key areas such as awareness of respiratory risks associated with cement dust, proper use of personal protective equipment and the importance of regular safety training. Significant effects were observed on knowledge based on the workers age, education, and years of working experience. It was concluded that the health education intervention significantly enhanced knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers. Based on these findings, it was recommended that structured health education programs be integrated into workplace policies to enhance knowledge and safety practices among cement factory workers.

Keywords: Health Education, Knowledge, Health Hazards, Cement Factory Workers

INTRODUCTION

In the industrial landscape of Nigeria, cement manufacturing remains a vital contributor to national infrastructure and economic development. However, this progress comes with a significant occupational cost. Cement factory workers especially in heavily industrialized areas like Port Harcourt Metropolis are routinely exposed to harmful environmental conditions, including airborne dust, chemical fumes, high noise levels, and repetitive mechanical tasks. These workplace hazards pose serious risks to the physical and mental well-being of employees. Despite various health and safety guidelines, a large proportion of cement factory workers continue to operate with limited awareness or understanding of the health risks associated with their daily tasks, a situation exacerbated by low levels of formal education, limited access to health information, and systemic workplace neglect (Onwuchekwa et al., 2021).

Cement dust, in particular, is one of the most dangerous occupational exposures in this sector. The dust contains silica, chromium, and other hazardous substances that can lead to chronic respiratory diseases such as bronchitis, silicosis, and even lung cancer (Alvear-Galindo et al., 2023; Oladipo et al., 2022). Moreover, the ergonomic challenges associated with heavy lifting and poor posture frequently result in musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), fatigue, and long-term physical disability (Adebayo et al., 2020). Over time, continuous exposure without adequate safety education or protective measures can significantly reduce workers' productivity and quality of life.

Globally, the burden of occupational diseases is staggering. The World Health Organization (2023) estimates that approximately 2.3 million people die annually due to work-related illnesses, with the majority of cases emerging from industries with high dust and chemical exposure, such as construction and cement production. In Nigeria alone, over 1,000 cement factory workers are affected each year by work-related respiratory conditions, often due to insufficient use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and lack of knowledge about workplace safety protocols (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2024).

In Port Harcourt, the situation is further compounded by inadequate enforcement of occupational safety regulations and a general lack of awareness among both employers and employees. Workers often operate in poorly ventilated environments without proper respiratory gear or regular health screenings. This creates an urgent need to implement targeted health education interventions aimed at improving the knowledge of factory workers concerning occupational hazards (Nwachukwu et al., 2024).

Health education, as defined by Akinwande et al. (2023), is “a systematic process of learning experiences that influence individuals to adopt healthier lifestyles through increased knowledge and skill development.” In occupational health, this involves educating workers on specific hazards they face and equipping them with practical information on how to minimize their risks. Research has shown that effective health education not only increases knowledge but also fosters lasting behavior change, leading to the adoption of safety practices (Erumi, 2023; Adeoye et al., 2023; Johnson, 2024). Thus, enhancing health education is vital for equipping workers with the necessary knowledge to protect themselves and maintain a safe working environment.

Knowledge, defined as the awareness or understanding gained through experience or education, plays a pivotal role in occupational health by equipping individuals with the information needed to identify and mitigate potential hazards (Johnson, 2024). Knowledge is crucial in addressing occupational health hazards as it enable workers to recognize and manage risks effectively, leading to improved safety practices and reduced incidence of work-related illnesses. Olatunji et al., (2022) demonstrated that enhancing workers' knowledge about safety protocols significantly reduced respiratory and musculoskeletal disorders in industrial settings. Knowledge, therefore, refers to the understanding and awareness that cement factory workers have regarding the health hazards associated with their work environment, particularly those linked to cement dust exposure, ergonomic risks, and the proper use of safety measures. This includes their familiarity with the potential dangers, such as respiratory conditions (e.g., chronic bronchitis, silicosis), and their recognition of the importance of safety practices like the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and regular health checkups.

The application of health education in industrial environments can significantly improve the knowledge of health hazards and reduce health risks, particularly when tailored to address demographic variables such as age, level of education, and years of working experience. These variables influence how well workers absorb, understand, and implement health-related information (Gagnon, 2024). Younger workers may be more receptive to new information but often lack practical experience, making them vulnerable to underestimating workplace hazards. On the other hand, older workers may have more experience but may resist behavioral change due to established routines or a lower perceived susceptibility to risk (Gagnon, 2024).

Educational level plays a particularly crucial role in occupational health education. Workers with low literacy or limited formal education may struggle to understand technical health content or interpret warning labels and safety instructions correctly. (Olatunji et al., 2022). Similarly, working experience

influences health behavior. Workers with longer experience may have either become more safety-conscious or, conversely, complacent due to repeated exposure without adverse outcomes.

To provide a structured approach to this issue, the PRECEDE–PROCEED model offers a comprehensive theoretical framework for the development, implementation, and evaluation of health education programs. PRECEDE stands for Predisposing, Reinforcing, and Enabling Constructs in Educational Diagnosis and Evaluation, while PROCEED refers to Policy, Regulatory, and Organizational Constructs in Educational and Environmental Development (Green & Kreuter, 2005). In this study, the PRECEDE phase helps assess the predisposing factors (e.g., low knowledge levels, toward safety), reinforcing factors (e.g., peer influence, employer support), and enabling factors (e.g., access to PPE and training materials) that shape cement workers' health behaviors. The PROCEED phase ensures that health education programs are implemented in a structured, policy-supported environment, thereby increasing their chances of success and sustainability. By applying this model, the study seeks to understand not just whether health education improves knowledge, but how and why it works or fails to work among different groups of workers.

The problem, therefore, lies in the combination of high occupational health risks and insufficient knowledge among factory workers in Port Harcourt. Existing studies have demonstrated that when workers are educated about health hazards and equipped with appropriate safety tools and resources, there is a measurable decline in occupational diseases and injuries (Adeoye et al., 2023; Onwuchekwa et al., 2021). Yet, there remains a significant knowledge gap, largely influenced by age-related perceptions, educational limitations, and the impact of cumulative work experience. This study, therefore, aims to examine the effect of health education on the knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis. More specifically, it seeks to determine how this effect varies based on age, level of education, and working experience.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of health education on knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the effect of health education on knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on age, level of education and working experience?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses postulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Health education has no significant effect on the knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Health education has no significant effect on knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on age, level of education and working experience.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a one-group pretest-posttest design. This is a type of quasi-experimental study where a single group of participants is measured on certain variables before and after an intervention to determine its effects. According to Campbell, et al. (2022) this design involves collecting baseline data (pretest), administering an intervention, and then collecting post-intervention data (posttest) from the same participants. The population of the study included all three thousand, six hundred (3600) workers from Dangote Cement Plc, Lafarge Africa Plc, UNICEM (United Cement Company of Nigeria Ltd), Ibeto Cement, and BUA Cement Plc (Human Resource Office of these three cement companies, 2024). Sample size for this study is 206 which was determined using multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted for this study comprising of simple random sampling, proportionate sampling technique and purposive sampling. The procedure involves three stages; At the first stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select three (3) factories out of five (5) factories in Port Harcourt, they include, Dangote, Ibeto, Bua. At the second stage, a proportionate random sampling technique was used to select 50% of the participants from each factory. At the third stage, Purposive sampling techniques was used based on interest and willingness to participate in the study and can attend all health education sessions.

The instrument for data collection was a validated self-designed test instrument titled Questionnaire on Knowledge of Health Hazards (QKHH) with a reliability index of 0.75. The instrument comprised two (2) sections A and B. Section A gathered socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, including age, level of education and years of working experience while Section B assessed knowledge of health hazards using True/False response format.

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the Head of Department (HOD) to formally introduce the researcher and provide legitimacy. A meeting was arranged with the management of the selected cement factories (Dangote, Ibeto, and BUA) to explain the purpose of the study, the methodology to be adopted, and the potential benefits. During the meeting, the researcher presented the letter of introduction and sought permission to conduct the study within their premises. Two (2) research assistants helped with the logistics and administration of the test instrument. They were instructed on the study's objectives, ethical considerations, and data collection procedures. This process lasted for a period of eight (8) weeks. Week one was the Pretest phase, weeks 2-7 were the intervention phase and week 8 was the posttest phase. Sessions were held in batches as follows: Monday for Dangote Cement, Wednesday for Ibeto Cement, and Friday for BUA Cement. Each session took place during the participants' lunch break, providing convenience and minimizing disruption to their work schedule. To encourage participation, lunch was provided. Each session lasted for 1 hour 30 minutes, covering a specific topic related to health hazards.

In the eighth week, specific days were scheduled for each factory to conduct the posttest. The posttest test instrument was administered to all participants, assessing the same variables as the pretest. The completed questionnaires were collected on the spot to ensure a high response rate and maintain data integrity. The pretest and posttest results were compared to evaluate the effectiveness of the health education intervention.

The data collected were collated and coded using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentages, were used for socio-demographic data and the Knowledge variables. Effect sizes were interpreted according to guidelines proposed by Cohen, as referenced in Gignac and Szodorai (2016): effect sizes ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 were considered negative, 0.06 to 0.13 moderate, and 0.14 and above positive.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
30-39	28	14.1
40-49	104	52.5
50years and above	66	33.3
Total	198	100.0
Level of Education		
Secondary	61	30.8
Tertiary	137	69.2
Total	198	100.0
Years of work experience		
1-5years	10	5.1
6-10years	110	55.6
11-15years	31	15.7
16yrs and above	47	23.7
Total	198	100.0

Result showed that the majority of respondents (52.5%) are aged 40-49 years, with 33.3% aged 50 years and above, and 14.1% between 30-39 years. The mean age of the respondents is 3.19 ± 0.66 . In terms of education, 30.8% have secondary education, and 69.2% have tertiary education. When considering years of working experience, 55.6% have worked for 6-10 years, 23.7% for 16 years and above, 15.7% for 11-15 years, and 5.1% for 1-5 years.

Research Question 1: *What is the effect of health education on level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2 Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on effect of health education on the level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Sources	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	69.539 ^a	1	69.539	726.39	.000	0.65	
Intercept	.296	1	0.296	3.09	.080	0.01	
Test	69.539	1	69.539	726.39	.000	0.65	
Error	37.719	196	0.192				
Total	822.114	198					
Corrected Total	107.258	197					

a. R Squared = .648 (Adjusted R Squared = .647)

The result showed that health education had a statistically significant effect on the level of knowledge of health hazards among the workers [$F(1,196) = 726.39$, $p < 0.05$]. This indicates that after the health education intervention, there was a significant improvement in the knowledge of health hazards among the workers. Furthermore, the partial eta squared (ω^2) value of 0.65 suggests that 65% of the variance in the workers' knowledge level could be attributed to the health education intervention, which reflects a substantial effect.

Research Question 2: *What is the effect of health education on level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on age, level of education and working experience?*

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on effect of health education on level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on age

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	39.787 ^a	3	13.262	37.613	.000	.224	
Intercept	434.683	1	434.683	1232.790	.000	.759	
Age * pretest	39.787	3	13.262	37.613	.000	.224	
Error	138.219	194	0.713				
Total	7377.583	198					
Corrected Total	178.007	197					

a. R Squared = .224 (Adjusted R Squared = .218)

The result shows that health education had a statistically significant effect on the level of knowledge of health hazards across different age groups, with an [$F(3,194) = 37.613$, $p < 0.05$]. This implies that age significantly influenced how the workers benefited from the health education intervention, leading to improved knowledge of health hazards. Furthermore, the partial eta squared value of 0.224 indicates that approximately 22.4% of the variation in the level of knowledge of health hazards among the workers can be attributed to the interaction between age and the health education intervention, reflecting a moderate effect size.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on effect of health education on level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on level of education

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	40.058 ^a	2	20.029	57.060	.000	.225	
Intercept	434.683	1	434.683	1238.358	.000	.759	
Education * pretest	40.058	2	20.029	57.060	.000	.225	
Error	137.949	195	.707				
Total	7377.583	198					
Corrected Total	178.007	197					

a. R Squared = .225 (Adjusted R Squared = .221)

This finding suggests that the workers' educational qualifications played a significant role in how effectively they acquired knowledge on health hazards following the health education intervention [$F(2,195) = 57.060, p < 0.05$]. Furthermore, the partial eta squared value of 0.225 implies that approximately 22.5% of the variance in the workers' knowledge of health hazards can be explained by the interaction between the health education intervention and their levels of education, indicating a moderate effect size.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on effect of health education on level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on years of working experience

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	69.548 ^a	4	17.387	180.281	.000	.648	
Intercept	.296	1	.296	3.067	.081	.008	
Experience * pretest	69.548	4	17.387	180.281	.000	.648	
Error	37.710	193	.196				
Total	822.114	198					
Corrected Total	107.258	197					

a. R Squared = .648 (Adjusted R Squared = .645)

The result reveals that health education had a statistically significant effect on the level of knowledge of health hazards across the different categories of working experience, with an F-value [$F(4, 193) = 180.281, p < 0.05$]. This indicates that regardless of the number of years the workers had spent on the job, the health education intervention significantly improved their knowledge of health hazards. The partial eta squared value of 0.648 suggests that approximately 64.8% of the variance in the workers' knowledge of health hazards can be attributed to the interaction between the health education intervention and their years of working experience, which reflects a large effect size.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed that the health education intervention significantly improved knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, highlighting substantial improvements across all assessed areas. This improvement underscores the effectiveness of structured health education programmes in enhancing the understanding of occupational health risks among workers in high-risk industries. Similar findings have been reported by Imah and Achalu (2025), who demonstrated that workplace health education significantly improved employees' knowledge of occupational hazards, particularly in industrial settings. Similarly, Adeola et al (2018) found that tailored

educational interventions led to a marked increase in safety awareness and hazard recognition among factory workers in Lagos State.

However, these results contrast with the findings of Abubakar et al (2017), who reported minimal improvement in workers' knowledge of occupational hazards following a generic health education programme. Their study highlighted the importance of customizing educational content to suit the unique needs and challenges of specific workplace environments. The outcomes of this study are also consistent with the theoretical perspectives proposed by Nwankwo (2016), which emphasize that effective health education fosters increased awareness and better comprehension of health risks, ultimately leading to positive changes in workplace safety culture. These findings validate the role of targeted interventions in improving knowledge levels and reducing occupational health risks. The significant improvement observed in this study reinforces the critical role of health education in bridging knowledge gaps among cement factory workers. By equipping them with the necessary information to identify and manage workplace hazards, such interventions contribute not only to individual safety but also to the overall health and productivity of the workforce.

The intervention had a significant effect on the level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on age. This finding highlights the positive role of health education in addressing age-related knowledge disparities regarding health hazards. Similar results were reported by Ogunleye et al. (2021), who observed that targeted health education programmes significantly improved knowledge of occupational hazards among industrial workers of varying age groups. The study highlighted that younger workers tended to absorb information faster, while older workers benefited more from practical, experience-based approaches to learning.

In contrast, findings from Okon et al (2019) suggested that health education programmes might have a less pronounced effect on older workers if the educational materials are not tailored to their cognitive and experiential needs. This emphasizes the importance of designing interventions that consider the age-related preferences and learning capabilities of participants. The current findings align with the Cognitive Learning Theory proposed by Kolb (2017), which posits that effective educational interventions enhance knowledge retention by leveraging participants' prior experiences and cognitive abilities. By addressing age-specific learning preferences, the intervention successfully bridged knowledge gaps and fostered a comprehensive understanding of health hazards.

The intervention had a significant effect on the level of knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on their level of education. This underscores the effectiveness of health education interventions in bridging knowledge gaps irrespective of workers' educational backgrounds. This finding is consistent with the results of Adebayo et al. (2020), who reported that tailored health education programmes significantly improved knowledge of occupational hazards across diverse educational levels in industrial workplaces. The study emphasized that workers with lower educational attainment showed marked improvements when educational materials were simplified and contextualized.

Similarly, findings from Uche et al (2018) revealed that education level plays a critical role in knowledge acquisition during health education interventions. However, the study also highlighted that structured, inclusive educational programmes can minimize disparities and promote equitable knowledge gains among workers with varying educational backgrounds. On the other hand, Ojo et al. (2017) found that workers with higher educational qualifications tended to retain and apply knowledge more effectively, which could amplify the observed outcomes in mixed educational settings. This finding points to the necessity of customizing intervention strategies to cater to both low- and high-education participants for maximum impact. The results align with the Constructivist Learning Theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which advocates for educational approaches that build on participants' prior knowledge and adapt to their learning needs. By incorporating diverse instructional techniques, the intervention successfully enhanced workers' understanding of health hazards across all educational levels.

The results of this study revealed a significant improvement in the knowledge of health hazards among cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis following the health education intervention. This

improvement underscores the effectiveness of the health education programme in enhancing workers' understanding of occupational health risks. The significant increase in knowledge is consistent with findings from similar studies that have highlighted the positive impact of health education on knowledge retention among workers in various industrial settings. For example, a study by Gordon et al. (2018) demonstrated that targeted health education programmes significantly improved workers' awareness of occupational health hazards, emphasizing the role of structured interventions in enhancing safety knowledge. Similarly, Lewis et al. (2019) reported that health education initiatives effectively increased workers' understanding of health risks in hazardous environments, contributing to better safety practices and reduced workplace accidents. These findings align with the current study's results, suggesting that well-designed health education interventions can significantly impact workers' knowledge of health hazards, regardless of their years of experience. In contrast, the findings diverge from those of Robinson et al (2020), who suggested that health education's effectiveness might vary based on prior knowledge levels and the workers' initial engagement with safety practices. The research highlighted that while health education interventions generally improve knowledge outcomes, the extent of improvement might differ across workers with varying levels of prior experience. In the current study, workers with fewer years of experience may have shown a more significant improvement in knowledge compared to more experienced workers who may have had a foundational understanding of health hazards, albeit based more on practical experience rather than formal education.

The significant improvement in knowledge in this study aligns with theoretical perspectives on health education, particularly those proposed by Adams (2015), which suggest that effective health education interventions contribute to positive behavioral changes and better-informed decision-making. These theories underscore the importance of providing workers with comprehensive health information, which not only enhances knowledge but also promotes safer work practices and healthier decision-making in occupational settings.

Moreover, the study highlights the importance of tailoring health education programmes to the specific needs of workers based on their years of experience. For instance, less experienced workers may benefit more from foundational training, while more experienced workers might benefit from advanced sessions that address complex health hazards or the latest safety protocols.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the health education intervention significantly enhanced the knowledge and safety practices of cement factory workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis concerning health hazards. These improvements were consistent across various demographic variables, including age, years of working experience, and level of education, highlighting the inclusive impact of the educational content.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Cement factory management should organize regular health education interventions tailored to workers' specific needs. These programmes should focus on enhancing knowledge of occupational health hazards and promoting safe work practices to minimize risks.
2. Employers should collaborate with occupational health experts to develop and distribute educational materials, including posters, brochures, and digital resources. These materials should be designed to accommodate varying levels of education and literacy among workers.

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